

Kinetic Behaviour of some Substituted-4-piperidones towards Oxidation by Aqueous Acidic CrO₃

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The kinetics of oxidation of *N*-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidone-4, *N*-methyl-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidone-4, *N*-methyl-3-ethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidone-4, *N*-methyl-3-isopropyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidone-4, and *N*-methyl-3,3-dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidone-4 by aqueous acidic CrO₃ have been carried out iodometrically under pseudo-first order conditions in the temperature range 35–50°. The oxidation reaction is found to be first order each with respect to oxidant and substrate. The rate increases with increase in [H⁺] and solvent composition (AcOH) in the reaction mixture. Increase of ionic strength (Na₂SO₄) increases the rate of reaction. Activation parameters have been evaluated from Arrhenius plot. The results are discussed in terms of a suitable mechanism involving a rate-determining formation of a chromate ester between CrO₃ and substrate followed by the rapid decomposition of the intermediate. The effect of 3-alkyl substituent has been analysed.

KINETICS of oxidation of a number of organic compounds by CrO₃ in acid medium have been studied¹. The similarity between cyclohexanone and piperidone (which is heterocyclohexanone) initiated the present investigation.

Experimental

The substituted-4-piperidones were prepared and purified following the literature procedure². All the reagents used were of analytical grade. Conductivity water was used in preparing all solutions. Glacial acetic acid unaffected by chromic acid was used. CrO₃ solution was prepared in conductivity water and standardised iodometrically. Piperidone solutions were prepared afresh by dissolving a weighed amount of each in acetic acid (A.R.). The pseudo-first order condition was maintained for all the kinetic runs by keeping the substrate and acid concentrations always in excess over that of CrO₃. The ionic strength was maintained by the addition of Na₂SO₄. The rates of oxidation were measured in 20% (v/v) acetic acid at 50° following the disappearance of the oxidant by iodometry for at least 50% utilisation of the oxidant and the results were found to be reproducible within ± 2% error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing an excess of CrO₃ to react with the piperidone and the unreacted CrO₃ estimated after completion of the reaction. The result showed that in acid medium, the stoichiometry could be expressed by equation (1).

The main product isolated in the reaction mixture was a dicarboxylic acid which was characterised by qualitative tests and ir and nmr spectral data.

Results and Discussion

Rate laws: At constant [H⁺] with the substrate in stoichiometric excess, plots of log [CrO₃] vs time are linear indicating a first order dependence of rate on [oxidant]. Contrary to expectations, the pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*₁) are found to decrease with the increase in [CrO₃] (Table 1). The rate of reaction increases with the increase in [piperidone] (Table 2). The second order rate constants (*k*₂) are calculated by dividing the pseudo-first order rate constants with the respective piperidone concentrations. The fairly concordant values of *k*₂ for all concentrations of piperidone indicate that the reaction is first order with respect to piperidone (Table 2). Plot of 1/*k*₁ vs 1/[piperidone] is a straight line passing through the origin indicating the absence of complex formation. The oxidation rate of 4-piperidone is directly proportional to [H⁺] (Table 3) and hence the order in the latter is unity. The plot of *k*₁ against [H⁺] gave a straight line with a positive intercept on the ordinate indicating the occurrence of acid dependent and

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [CrO₃] ON REACTION RATE
[Piperidone]=1.0 × 10⁻³ M, [H⁺]=0.5 M, μ=1.8 M, Solvent=20% AcOH+80% H₂O, Temp.=50°

[CrO ₃] × 10 ³ M	<i>k</i> ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0.5	1.80
1.0	1.40
1.5	1.20
2.0	0.77

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING [PIPERIDONE] ON REACTION RATE

$[\text{CrO}_3]=1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+]=0.5 \text{ M}$, $\mu=1.8 \text{ M}$, Solvent=20% AcOH+80% H_2O , Temp.=50°

[Piperidone] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	k_1 $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	k_2 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$
0.5	6.5	1.30
1.0	14.0	1.40
1.5	19.0	1.26
2.0	26.3	1.32

 TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING $[\text{H}^+]$ ON REACTION RATE

[Piperidone]= $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{CrO}_3]=1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $\mu=1.8 \text{ M}$, Solvent=20% AcOH+80% H_2O , Temp.=50°

$[\text{H}^+]$ M	k_1 $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_2/[\text{H}^+]$ $\text{M}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$
0.25	7.7	0.030
0.50	14.0	0.028
0.75	26.0	0.035
1.00	34.0	0.034

acid independent processes concurrently. From the slope of the above plot the acid dependent rate constant k_a and from the intercept the acid independent rate constant k_b were evaluated. From the relation $k' = k_a [\text{H}^+] + k_b$, k' was calculated: $k_a = \text{slope}/[\text{piperidone}] = 3.33 \text{ M}^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$, $k_b = \text{intercept}/[\text{piperidone}] = 15.00 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, $k' = k_a [\text{H}^+] + k_b = 16.67 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. In accordance with the observations made the rate is given by the equation,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = k [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] [\text{piperidone}] [\text{H}^+]$$

Effect of temperature on the pseudo-first order rate constants: The reaction was carried out at four different temperatures in the range 35–50°. Increasing temperature enhances the rate of reaction (Table 4). The activation parameters evaluated from Arrhenius plot are $E_a = 62.23 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_{\ddagger}^\circ = 59.54 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_{\ddagger}^\circ = -237.44 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G_{\ddagger}^\circ = 136.24 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $Z = 1.2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$.

Influence of ionic strength: The increase in ionic strength (Na_2SO_4) from 1.65 to 2.1 M increased the rate constant (Table 4) showing the participation of charged particles in the rate determining step⁸.

Effect of varying solvent composition of medium: Increasing amounts of acetic acid in the reaction mixture increased the rate of oxidation (Table 4). This may probably be due to the ion-dipole interaction of the reactants⁴, which was confirmed by a linear plot of $\log k$ against $1/D$.

Effect of change in structure on order of reactivity: The 3-alkyl-substituted-1-hetero-4-cyclohexanols have shown to exist in the anchored chair formation with the alkyl and phenyl groups in the most stable equatorial position⁵. The same can be expected in 3-alkyl-1-hetero-4-piperidones. The CrO_3 oxidation relieves the non-bonded steric interactions of the vicinal alkyl group and hence

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARYING TEMPERATURE, IONIC STRENGTH AND SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON REACTION RATE

[Piperidone]= $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{CrO}_3]=1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+]=0.5 \text{ M}$

Temp. °C	$[\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4]$ M	AcOH %	k_1 $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
35	1.8	20	6.4
40	1.8	20	7.2
45	1.8	20	9.2
50	1.8	20	14.0
50	1.65	20	11.0
50	1.95	20	18.0
50	2.10	20	25.0
50	1.80	30	15.0
50	1.80	40	18.0
50	1.80	50	21.0

3-alkyl substituent enhances the rate. The plots of $\log [\text{CrO}_3]$ vs time (Fig. 1) for five different substituted-4-piperidones give the rate constant sequence as $k_{\text{ethyl}} > k_{\text{methyl}} > k_{\text{isopropyl}} > k_{\text{unsubstituted}} > k_{\text{dimethyl}}$ (Table 5). This indicates that Me–OH non-bonded interaction is essential in the oxidation reactivity of the molecule. This interaction is greater in 3-ethyl

 Fig. 1. Plots of $\log [\text{CrO}_3]$ vs time of substituted-4-piperidones.

than in 3-methyl due to its larger size. Correspondingly, Me–OH interaction is increased in 3-ethyl. Irrespective of the larger size, 3-isopropyl has a low rate. This may be due to the lowering of the essential Me–OH interaction by the Ph–Me interactions present in two of its three conformations in the equilibrium mixture. This interaction may result in the distortion of the chair conformation. In this oxidation reaction, 3,3-dimethyl is found to be least reactive. Presence of two methyl groups on the adjacent carbon atom of the reaction centre has a hindering effect due to distorted chair

conformation. Indeed we tried with 6-different 3-substituted-N-methyl-4-piperidones but for the sixth one, N-methyl-3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidone-4 we could not measure the reaction rate due to salting-out effect.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF CHANGE OF STRUCTURE OF SUBSTRATE ON REACTION RATE

Conformation		k_1 $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
A	$R=\text{CH}_3, R'=R''=\text{CH}_3$	0.25
B	$R=\text{CH}_3, R'=\text{CH}_3, R''=\text{H}$	1.40
C	$R=\text{CH}_3, R'=\text{O}_2\text{H}_5, R''=\text{H}$	1.50
D	$R=\text{CH}_3, R'=(\text{OH})_2\text{CH}; R''=\text{H}$	1.00
E	$R=\text{CH}_3, R'=R''=\text{H}$	0.51

Test for free radicals: Addition of methyl methacrylate to the oxygen-free reaction mixture does not give rise to any polymer suggesting the absence of radical intermediates and the reaction to follow a polar type mechanism.

Mechanism: Aqueous solutions of chromic acid may contain several species, and the following equilibrium

Scheme 1

is the most important. The decrease in the rate constant with the increase in $[\text{CrO}_3]$ in the present investigation suggests that the most probable active oxidising species can be HCrO_4^- . Based on the above experimental observations and from the conclusion that the oxidation of piperidone and cyclohexanone by H_2CrO_4 follow similar mechanisms as expected from the similarity in their structures, the mechanism involving nucleophilic attack of CrO_3 on the enol form of piperidone as the slow rate determining step may be proposed (Scheme 1).

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